

Green Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles and its Application as Nanofertilizer

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Abstract:

*Nanotechnology represents a rapidly expanding global market. Achieving eco-friendly, high-yield, cost effective, and sustainable production of nanoparticles remains a significant hurdle. This research addresses these challenges by employing Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaf extract and chlorophyll as natural reducing and capping agents for the green synthesis of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs). For a comparison, synthesis of AgNPs was carried out by a chemical approach where trisodium citrate and polyvinyl alcohol were used as the reducing and capping agents respectively. The synthesis of AgNPs was confirmed by UV-spectrophotometric analysis, which revealed a characteristic absorption peak localized between 420 and 450 nm. To assess the efficacy of AgNPs as nanofertilizers, their impact on the seed germination of *Triticum aestivum* (wheat) was systematically evaluated. Subsequent analysis revealed that the green synthesized AgNPs exhibited superior efficacy compared to their chemically synthesized counterparts. *Triticum aestivum* seeds treated with biogenic AgNPs displayed significant enhancements in physiological and biochemical markers, including increased root and shoot elongation, as well as elevated levels of sugar, protein, chlorophyll, and carotenoids. Thus, green synthesized AgNPs possess the ability of nanofertilizer and can be used for agricultural applications.*

Keywords: *Green Synthesis, Silver Nanoparticles, Nanofertilizer, Azadirachta indica, Triticum aestivum.*

Introduction:

Nanotechnology is an interdisciplinary subject which involves nanoparticles of size in the range of 1 to 100 nm. The unique characteristics of nanoparticles is attributed because of its high surface to volume ratio¹. The word ‘nano’ is derived from ‘nanos’ which is of Greek origin, that means ‘dwarf’. Hence, simply nanotechnology can be defined as technology at small scale. Although in the scientific community the word nano is called as 1 billionth of a meter, which is simply termed as a ‘nanometer’. A Nobel prize winner Richard P. Feynman, who was a physicist, presented the vision of nanotechnology for the very first time. He elaborated the wide application of significant mechanistic tools and objects having small size,

as he had a strong belief that ‘there is plenty of room at the bottom’². In today's era apart from physicists, several scientists belonging from numerous fields have a strong belief that nanoscale manufacturing instrumentation and technologies like nanomedicine, diagnostic devices, nanomachines and robotics etc. will definitely create a miraculous future. Nanoparticles hold extremely unique characteristics which have been used in various fields such as agriculture, electronics and healthcare services. The synthesis of nanoparticles can be done by using chemical, physical and biological methods. Although, the former two methods exerts harmful effects on the environment, demands labour work and often becomes expensive. Properties such as

affordability, environmental friendliness, fast rate of synthesis, no requirement of high temperatures and hazardous chemicals makes a green synthesis method more beneficial over the conventional methods³. Hence, the biological method which is often termed as ‘Green Synthesis Method’ offers an eco-friendly, affordable, and beneficial approach by overcoming the drawbacks of physical and chemical synthesis methods.

Plants are known as chemical factories of nature which are cost-efficient and need little maintenance. Plant extracts in particular have been extensively used for the synthesis of metal and metal oxide nanoparticles, and this is due to the presence of essential phytochemicals in plant extracts especially from the leaves. Leaf extract contains various types of phytochemicals such as terpenoids, flavonoids, ketones, aldehydes, amides, and carboxylic acids, which play a major role in formulating and enhancing the bioactivity of the nanoparticles⁴. Synthesis of NPs using plant extracts has been reported in several plant species. A wide range of molecules, ranging from proteins to various low molecular weight compounds such as terpenoids, alkaloids, amino acids, alcoholic compounds, polyphenols (catechin, flavones, taxifolin, procyanidins of various chain lengths formed by catechin and epicatechin units, and phenolic acids), glutathiones, polysaccharides, antioxidants, organic acids (ascorbic, oxalic, malic, tartaric, and protocatechuic acid), quinones etc., have been reported to play a role in the green synthesis of NPs. The participation of sugars, terpenoids, polyphenols, alkaloids, phenolic acids, and proteins in the reduction of metal ions into NPs and in supporting their subsequent stability has also been postulated⁵. Plant extracts have the ability to produce NPs with defined size, shape, and composition. Furthermore, the presence of a wide array of phytochemicals in their extract may function as natural stabilizing and reducing agents

for NPs production. It is accepted that plant-derived NPs are also less likely to cause harmful side effects in humans when compared to chemically synthesized NPs, and exhibit a high biological potential with applications in agriculture, food science and technology, bioengineering, cosmetic or nanomedicine, and human health protection⁶.

Chlorophyll is the primary pigment found within algae and plants, responsible for driving photosynthesis. This molecule captures solar energy to facilitate the chemical transformation of water and carbon dioxide into oxygen and glucose, serving as a vibrant visual marker of vital biological activity. The presence of active methyl, ketone, carboxylic, and aldehyde functional groups makes chlorophyll a versatile, inexpensive precursor for stabilization and functionalization of nanoparticles⁷. The research carried out by Khan et al. (2022), shows that integration of chlorophyll with CuO NPs significantly augments antimicrobial efficacy through a synergistic interaction between the pigment and liberated copper ions. This composite effectively inhibits microbial proliferation, suggesting high potential for applications in biomedical engineering and food preservation technology⁸. Moreover, research have shown that, the potential of AgNPs to act as a nanofertilizer is due to their ability to increases key metabolites such as salicylic acid, glycerol-3-phosphate and niacinamide, which are important in the stress response. Furthermore, metabolic pathway analysis revealed that AgNPs activate critical pathways related to hormone signaling, glutathione metabolism, and the biosynthesis of flavone and flavonols⁹. Hence, the present research focuses on synthesis of AgNPs using chlorophyll and leaf extract of *Azadirachta indica* providing a comparative effect of chemically synthesized AgNPs and Green synthesized AgNPs on *Triticum aestivum*.

Materials and Methods:**1. Green synthesis of AgNPs:**

The leaves of neem were collected from the campus of institute which were further thoroughly washed with distilled water to remove unwanted debris. The leaves were further air dried at room temperature. After that 20 grams of neem leaves were chopped finely and subjected for boiling in 100 ml distilled water at 70°C for 30 min. Finally the extract was allowed to cool down to room temperature and was filtered. Now from this, 20 ml of leaf extract was taken and added to 80 ml of 5mM AgNO₃ which was prepared in distilled water. This solution was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 mins. The pellet and supernatant were separated of which the pellet was dried and used for further absorbance measurements. Also, to synthesize chlorophyll mediated AgNPs, 30 ml of chlorophyll solution (A665) was added to 100 ml of 5mM AgNO₃. The mixture was subjected to 600 W of microwave power for 10 s. The resulting solution was then allowed to cool at room temperature.

2. Chemical synthesis of AgNPs:

In a clean dry test tube, 4.5 ml of 5mM AgNO₃ and 0.5 ml polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) as capping agent was added. This tube was kept in a boiling water bath at 80 to 90°C and immediately 0.5 ml 0.1% trisodium citrate was added directly. The tubes were kept in a boiling water bath for 10 mins and then centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 mins. The pellet was collected and used for absorbance measurements.

3. Characterization of synthesized AgNPs :

All synthesized AgNPs were monitored by UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Agilent G6860A Cary-60).

4. Effect of AgNPs on wheat seed germination:

The effect of chemically synthesized and green synthesized AgNPs on wheat seed germination was determined by the petri plate method. The wheat seeds were surface sterilized

by using 0.1% sodium hypochlorite solution for about 2–4 min, then washed for 2 times with distilled water, and allowed to be soaked in prepared AgNPs solutions for half an hour. The seeds were shifted to sterilized Petri plates containing filter paper and placed at equidistance which was incubated at room temperature for about two weeks. The seed germination percentage was measured by using the formula given below.

Germination percentage = Number of seeds germinated / Total number of seeds × 100

5. Plant growth parameter analysis:

A small pot experiment (Fig.1) was carried out to study the growth parameters viz. root length, shoot length, estimation of sugar, protein, chlorophyll and carotenoid content of plants. The plants were carefully removed from the pots after 10 days of transplantation and used for further studies. The reducing sugar content and protein content of plants was determined by using the 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid (DNSA)¹⁰ and Biuret¹¹ method respectively. The estimation of chlorophyll content and carotenoids was performed by grinding one gram of fresh leaves with 80% acetone using mortar and pestle, which was further centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 mins. The supernatant was collected and absorbance was taken at 480, 645, 663 nm. The total chlorophyll and carotenoids were measured by using the method given by Arnon (1949)¹² and Davies (1976)¹³.

Fig.1: Growth of wheat seeds treated with (a) control with distilled water, (b) only AgNO_3 , (c) chemically synthesized AgNPs, (d) neem leaf extract mediated AgNPs, (e) chlorophyll mediated AgNPs

Results and Discussion:

1. Characterization of synthesized AgNPs:

The formation of AgNPs was evidenced by the colour transition, progressing from a faint to yellowish-brown, then reddish-brown, and ultimately achieving a stable colloidal brown (Fig.2). These visual observations are consistent with the previous findings confirming successful synthesis of silver nanoparticles^{14,15}. The characterization of the biosynthesized AgNPs was performed using UV–Vis spectrophotometer (Agilent G6860A Cary-60), which showed an absorbance peak localized between 420 and 450 nm, indicating the presence of AgNPs (Fig.3). This spectral feature is attributed to strong localized surface plasmon resonance (SPR), a phenomenon which is characteristic of metallic nanoparticles.

Fig.2: Colloidal preparations of AgNPs.

Fig.3: UV-vis absorption spectra of AgNPs synthesized in laboratory

2. Plant Growth Parameter Analysis:

The effect of green synthesized AgNPs on wheat plant development was thoroughly evaluated through the analysis of multiple plant growth parameters. Photosynthetic pigments are very crucial parameters, and their amount present in the plant leaves demonstrates the overall plant health. This study explored the impact of green synthesized AgNPs using neem leaf extract and chlorophyll on the wheat plant's total chlorophyll, carotenoid, sugar and protein content compared to the group of chemically synthesized AgNPs and control. The germination percentage of plants treated with green synthesized AgNPs using neem leaf extract and chlorophyll was 100%, which was greater than chemically synthesized AgNPs and AgNO_3 group i.e 50%, 70% respectively. The total chlorophyll as well as carotenoid content of plants treated with green synthesized AgNPs using neem leaf extract and chlorophyll was 0.244 and 0.261 mg/gm respectively, which was significantly enhanced after the application of green synthesized AgNPs. The total chlorophyll as well as carotenoid content of the chemically synthesized AgNPs, only AgNO_3 group and control group was found to be less i.e 0.165, 0.213, 0.230 mg/gm respectively. The sugar content of the plants treated with green synthesized AgNPs using neem leaf extract and chlorophyll was 3.238 and 2.992 mg/gm

respectively; The protein content of the plants treated with green synthesized AgNPs using neem leaf extract and chlorophyll was 4.1 and 4.0 mg/gm respectively, which was remarkably increased as compared to chemically synthesized

AgNPs which was 1.436 and 1.5 mg/gm sugar and protein content respectively. The Graph 1 and Graph 2 below elucidates morphological and biochemical parameter analysis.

Conclusion:

In this study AgNPs are synthesized by using *A. indica* leaf extracts and chlorophyll pigment as natural reducing and capping agents, which is a cost-effective, eco-friendly and easy method. The germination percentage of seeds,

root and shoot length, total chlorophyll, carotenoid, sugar and protein content of seeds treated with green synthesized AgNPs was highest followed by the seeds treated with control and chemically synthesized AgNPs. Thus, this

demonstrates that green synthesized AgNPs acts as an efficient source of Nanofertilizer.

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